

Plasmonic wave assessment via optomechatronics system for biosensor application

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ABSTRAC

Transduction biosensor (mass-based, optical and electrochemical) involves analysis, recognition and amplification in the acquired sample. In this work, the plasmonic-based biosensor was employed without using tags. It is crucial to determine angles of Brewster (Θ_b) and critical (Θ_c) for generating plasmonic resonance (Θ_r). The objective is to verify a cost-effective plasmonic biosensor through Fresnel simulation and experimentation of a developed optomechatronics system. The borosilicate glass, Au and Air layers were simulated with the Winspall 3.02 simulator. The optomechatronics system consists of: 1-optics (650 nm laser, slit, polarizer, photodiode), 2-mechanical (bipolar stepper motors, gears, stages) and 3-electronics (PIC18F4550, liquid crystal display (LCD) and drivers). Later, the software performs angular interrogation by reading the reflected beam from a rotating prism at 0.1125. Experimentation to simulation accuracy indicates that percentage differences for Θ_r and Θ_c are 1% and 0.2%, respectively. In conclusion, excellence verification was successfully achieved between experimentation and simulation. It proved that the low-cost optomechatronics system is capable and reliable to be deployed for the biosensor application.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Biosensors quantify biological signals via bio-recognition, bio-transducer, and electronics systems [1]. Many biosensors require labeling substances such as fluorescent, isotopic, chemiluminescent, radioactive, quantum dot, antibodies, nanoparticles, and enzymes [2]. Purchasing test kits and labeling molecules for a biosensor will incur extra costs [3], [4]. Conversely, plasmonic-based biosensors promote a label-free method for instant measurement, cheaper procedures, low sample volume, high sensitivity and specificity [5], [6]. Unfortunately, more is required to know about the production of the plasmonic wave for a label-free biosensor. It becomes relevant to assess a beam reflectivity for verifying the plasmonic wave under reference to angles of Brewster, critical and resonance. Demand for reliable, low-cost biosensors is rising globally due to rising healthcare costs [7]. However, a low-cost biosensor without compromising system accuracy is highly desirable.

Therefore, a strategy for cost-effectiveness plasmonic-based biosensors should be reported via 3D printing for the optomechanics system. Label-free biosensors are tested for optical, dielectric permittivity, acoustic, electrochemical, and electrical impedance [8]–[11]. During the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic, research in optical biosensors was expedited for coronavirus [6]. The modulation/transduction methods assessed/evaluated optical properties (transmission, absorption, reflection, refraction, scattering, and plasmonic) [12]. Later, these properties are applied in optical biosensor applications such as plasmonic, spectroscopy, colorimetric, interferometric, luminescent, fluorescent and evanescent waves [13]. Optical biosensors monitor affinity, binding kinetics, concentration, and specificity [14]. Bio-receptors for the optical biosensor include antibodies, aptamers, enzymes, nuclear acids, and molecularly imprinted polymers [15]–[19].

Bioreceptors replicate physiological interactions to bind chemicals on sensor surfaces [19]. Optical-bioreceptor have benefits in biotechnology, nanotechnology, molecular biology, microbiology, virology, and chemistry [20]. Optical, mechanical, and electronics collaboration allows spectral investigation on dielectric-metal interfaces [21], [22]. The collaboration synchronizes opto-mechanical positions for high-accuracy and repeatability measurements. Photons at total internal reflection (TIR) excite a positive-negative permittivity of the dielectric-metal interfaces to create plasmonic energy [23]. Photon intensity is significantly reduced by plasmonic energy absorption [24]. This phenomenon is known as a resonance angle caused by the penetration of plasmonic energy from lower to upper interfaces of dielectric-metal [25]. It is proportional to the refractive index of any biological substance deposited on the metal interface. An optical biosensor with computational validation for *Escherichia coli* (E.coli) was carried out. It consists of functionalized (polyclonal anti-E.coli antibody) polymer optical fiber (POF), light emitting diode (LED), photodetector and data acquisition (DAQ) card. Detection of E-coli is successfully obtained with a concentration of 104 CFU/ml. However, a characteristic of hydrophilic or hydrophobic contact on the antigenic regions must be pre-identified for epitope prediction with computer validation [26].

In a similar work, a selective and sensitive biosensor had been designed with the photonic crystal for ethanol and methanol detection. A different concentration of ethanol/ methanol percentages correlated with a change in the refractive indexes (r.i). Ethanol/methanol with water mixtures shows different detection spectra at 1.2/1.4 nm with 1.3326/1.36212 r.i from 1,369 to 1,391.5 nm of resonance wavelength [27]. High sensitivity, quality factor, figure of merit and transfer coefficient were achieved respectively at 750 nm/RIU, 1000, 561 RIU⁻¹ and 97%. However, no linearity between densities and refractive index was recorded for different alcohol percentages.

Despite the availability of numerous biosensors in the market, the optomechanics system presents a viable alternative to existing commercial solutions. The objectives are to i) develop a cost-effective plasmonic-based biosensor and ii) assess/validate the existence of the plasmonic wave via Fresnel simulation/optomechanics system, respectively.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This section discusses the simulation and development of optomechanics for optics, mechanical systems, and electronic systems. The optics involve a p-polarized beam for Transverse Magnetic transmission. The p-polarized beam then hits the prism and reflects to a photodiode in a single rotation. Therefore, the prism-photodiode was positioned and aligned mechanically on rotational stages. The photodiode converts the received beam into voltages and feeds to the electronics section. The section performs: i) photodiode digitization, ii) stepper motor synchronization, and iii) serial transmission of reflective data to the computer.

2.1. Simulation

Winspall is a software to simulate reflectivity curves as expressed by the Fresnel equation in (1) and (2). The equations determine electromagnetic wave transmission and reflection at different refractive index mediums (n_1 and n_2) and permeability (μ_1 and μ_2).

$$r_p = \frac{(n_1/\mu_1) \cos \theta_t - (n_2/\mu_2) \cos \theta_i}{(n_1/\mu_1) \cos \theta_t + (n_2/\mu_2) \cos \theta_i} \quad (1)$$

$$t_p = \frac{2(n_2/\mu_2) \cos \theta_i}{(n_1/\mu_1) \cos \theta_t + (n_2/\mu_2) \cos \theta_i} \quad (2)$$

The simulation parameter offers permittivity ($\epsilon' + i\epsilon''$) or refractive index ($n + ik$), respectively for inputting layers thickness/ dielectric constant or layer thickness/ refractive index. As shown in Table 1, different dielectric layers are used to simulate plasmonic resonance.

Table 1. Dielectric constant

layers	Medium	Thickness (nm)	EpsX-real	EpsX-imaginary
1	BK7 glass	0	2.29	0
2	Gold (Au)	50	-12.45	1.3
3	Air	0	1	0

2.2. Optomechanics system

The system in Figure 1 consists of several operating interfaces such as optics, electronics, mechanical and PC-based control systems. Thorlabs laser diode (650 nm, 7 mW) was chosen as a monochromatic light source. Two aspheric lenses ($f = 20.1$ mm) converged the light source to the thin gold (Au) film at 50 nm. Adjustable aperture control via the iris was aligned and positioned accurately to reduce the diffraction effect. A linear polarizer is vital to assure TM or P-polarized excitation under a Brewster angle, as expressed in (3) [4].

$$\theta_B = \tan^{-1}(n_2/n_1) \quad (3)$$

Two prisms (coated Au layer at 50 nm and non-coated) were tested for acquiring p-polarized light and generating plasmonic resonance. They were placed on a rotating optical stage to achieve a reflectivity profile via a photodiode from 30° to 80° of the incidence angles.

Figure 1. Optics schematic diagram

The mechanical design in the Figure 2 is based on replaceable modular parts such as gears, stages, stands, plates, cages, bases, couplers, holders and sockets. The annular gear (AG) functions as the photodiode (PD) stage and is coupled to the running gear (RG). The RG was fitted to the stepper motor and housed with dual support gears (SG). Due to the expensive optic components in the market, 3D models are respectively shown on Side/ Top views in Figure 2(a) and Figure 2(b) were designed and sliced.

Figure 2. Design of optomechanics system: (a) side view and (b) top view

The electronic system in Figure 3 converts acquired reflectance from the photodiode (PD) at a $1.6 \mu\text{s}$ interval via an onboard 10-bit analog digital converter (ADC)'s PIC18F4550. The ADC reference

voltage was set to 2 V for 1.95 mV ADC resolution to satisfy PD’s voltage range. The ADC results were sampled and averaged 150 times to eliminate fluctuation due to the 50 Hz power line interference. Then, ADC’s result was sent to the personal computer (PC) at 19,200 bps via asynchronous serial. Apart from ADC reception, the PC interface also: 1- Choose 18 modes of the stepper motor, 2- control and synchronize the stepper motor (SM1 and SM2), 3- Data logging and 4- Digital filtering for smoothing ADC data with Savitzky Golay as expressed in (4).

$$y_t = \frac{(-2x_{t-3}+3x_{t-2}+6x_{t-1}+7x_t+6x_{t+1}+3x_{t+2}-2x_{t+3})}{21} \tag{4}$$

Figure 3. Electronic system for optomechatronics system

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in Figure 4, the mechanical system had been fabricated and assembled. The photodiode (PD) stage was retrofitted to the annular gear (AG), and the prism was placed on the rotational stage (RS). The gear teeth at a 2.5 ratio for AG and running gear (RG) are set to 145 and 58, respectively.

Different trains of pulses (Top trace) were generated in Figure 5 for AG at every T-pulse (Bottom trace) of the rotational stage (RS). The generated number of AG’s pulses (ps) was changed from 2ps to 3ps at T intervals to fulfill the 2.5 gear ratio. It synchronizes PD/ RS at 0.1125°/0.045° resolution for 3,200/8,000 steps on a single rotation, respectively.

Figure 4. Fabricated and assembled of an optomechatronics system with a 3D printer

Figure 5. Stepper motor pulses for the photodiode stage and prism stage

The P-polarized wave was confirmed with a non-coated prism, as observed as a reflectivity trace (dash line) in Figure 6. When the incidence angle (θ_i) gradually increases, the reflectivity decreases until it hits zero intensity at Brewster angle (θ_B). Beyond θ_B , the θ_i keeps rising until the transmitted angle (θ_t) is equal to 90° . At this point, reflectivity becomes saturated for the total internal reflection (TIR) condition at $\theta_i > \theta_{c2}$. Therefore, a linear polarizer (400~700 nm) was rotated via rotation mount (RSP1/M) for generating P-polarized light at Brewster's angle. Meanwhile, a solid line in Figure 6 represents a reflective trace from a 50 nm gold (Au) layer coated on the prism. A maximum attenuation was observed at the resonance angle (θ_{res}) due to the excitation of plasmonic energy beyond the critical angle (θ_{c1}). However, the plasmonic energy could not be generated from the non-coated prism as observed from a flat reflectivity trace beyond the critical angle (θ_{c2}). Resonance occurs when energy conservation (angular frequency of incident light) matches the momentum (k-propagation) for generating the plasmonic energy.

In Figure 7, the experimentation result indicates reflectivity curves from the photodiode at different reflected angles and stepper motor steps. Measured reflectivity traces via the developed optomechanronics system were plotted in Figure 7(a) and Figure 7(b) for the non-coated and Au-coated prism (50 nm), respectively.

Figure 6. P-polarized on Brewster's and resonance angle

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Measured reflectivity traces from (a) bare prism and (b) coated prism with 50 nm Au layer

Referring to the Figure 8, images of the reflected beams from coated (50 nm gold layer) and non-coated prism were captured by a compact complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) camera at 43°. Lower/higher RGB values in Table 2 indicate the presence/absence of the plasmonic energy, as shown in Figure 8(a) and Figure 8(b), respectively. a signal processing technique via least fitting polynomial successfully smoothing noisy data in Figure 9. A high-frequency fluctuation was observed in Figure 9(a) and smoothed out until ten filtering stages in Figure 9(b) with the Savitzky-Golay (SG) algorithm.

Table 2. RGB values of the reflected beam

Prism	Angle	Mean values			SD values		
		R	G	B	R	G	B
Au Coated (50 nm)	43	40.82	8.83	20.57	41.35	3.75	4.68
Non-coated	43	139.66	38.84	56.17	93.65	83.13	80.71

Figure 8. Images from (a) coated prism with 50 nm Au layer and (b) non-coated prism

Figure 9. Reflective traces (a) before filter and (b) after SG filtering

4. CONCLUSION

3D printing modular optomechanics system components reduced development costs. Modular printing and assembly were made possible. Generating plasmonic energy under P-polarization satisfies the boundary condition of the metal-dielectric interfaces. The reflectivity trace indicates a resonance angle at 42.7° (θ_{res}), while critical angles for coated (θ_{c1}) and non-coated (θ_{c2}) prism were observed at 39°. The absence of a thin gold layer at 50 nm could not generate the plasmonic energy. Vice versa, the coated thin layer at 50 nm on the prism indicates maximum attenuation immediately beyond the critical angle. A low-cost 3D-printed optomechanics device was shown to be a reliable, accurate, and efficient plasmonic-based biosensor.

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